

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Achilov Rustam Anvar o'g'li

INTRAKTIV DASTURIY VOSTALAR YARTISH VA UN DAN FOYDALANISH

METODIKASI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/APREL

